

fed normally on Reihou, 47% could feed on IR26, and 1% could feed on IR26, IR42, and Reihou. Average honeydew excreted daily was about 46 ± 23 mg on Reihou and 33 ± 18 mg on IR26, respectively. Only one female excreted 49 mg on IR42. Five females excreted

more than 10 mg on IR26, but less than 10 mg on Reihou and IR42 (see figure).

We conclude that about half of the recent BPH immigrants to Japan were biotype 2, and the rest were still biotype 1. ■

Detoxifying enzymes of the brown planthopper (BPH)

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Among the major detoxifying enzymes, hydrolases are the most studied group because of their involvement in the resistance of *Nilaparvata lugens* Stål to both organophosphorus and pyrethroid insecticides. Activity of carboxylesterase toward 1-naphthyl acetate in BPH is at least 20-fold higher than in some lepidoptera. More than a dozen carboxylesterase isozymes have been resolved using isoelectric-focusing electrophoresis, and substrate specificity has been observed in some isozymes.

Considerable conjugation of 1-chloro-2,4-dinitrobenzene mediated by glutathione transferase has been observed in BPH. This enzyme in the pest, however, does not show any detectable activity toward another model substrate, 1,2-dichloro-4-nitrobenzene, or insecticides (parathion, paraoxon, and methyl parathion) known to be substrates

for glutathione transferase in other insects.

Activity of microsomal P450-dependent monooxygenases toward several model substrates in BPH is very low—only about 1/50 to 1/100 of that in some lepidopterous insects. It has been hypothesized that this low monooxygenase activity may be due to its contact with only water-soluble materials in plant saps (see table).

The metabolic mechanisms of insecticide resistance observed in BPH may reflect the fundamental makeup of detoxifying enzymes. A lack of cross-resistance in BPH from existing organophosphorus/pyrethroid resistance (conferred by enhanced carboxylesterase hydrolysis) to buprofezin might be because the carboxylesterases do not hydrolyze this chitin synthesis inhibitor. Further, there may not be active microsomal monooxygenases with which to hydroxylate buprofezin, a known detoxifying reaction observed in soils. If resistance to buprofezin should occur in BPH, it might be the result of target site alterations. ■

Activities of detoxifying enzymes of *Nilaparvata lugens* Stal.

Enzyme and substrate	Specific activity
Carboxylesterase	
1-naphthyl acetate	40.2 $\mu\text{mol}/\text{min}$ per mg protein
2-naphthyl acetate	36.9 $\mu\text{mol}/\text{min}$ per mg protein
Glutathione transferase	
1-chloro-2,4-dinitrobenzene	192 $\mu\text{mol}/\text{min}$ per mg protein
1,2-dichloro-4-nitrobenzene	ND ^a
Parathion	ND
Paraoxon	ND
Methyl parathion	ND
Microsomal P450-monooxygenases	
Aldrin	3.75 pmol/min per mg protein
Methoxyresorufin	2.90 pmol/min per mg protein
Ethoxyresorufin	ND
Ethoxycoumarin	ND

^aND = not detected.

Integrated pest management—other pests

Efficacy of benomyl in controlling the ufra nematode in Vietnam

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We conducted two experiments to test the effect of benomyl on the ufra nematode, *Ditylenchus angustus*, in deepwater rice in farmers' fields.

The first experiment was conducted in the village of Long Thanh My, Thu Duc district, Ho Chi Minh City. The farmer transplanted 45-d-old seedlings of variety Tieu doi in an ufra-prone area. Eight benomyl treatments were evaluated.

The second experiment was conducted, in Dong Phu, Chau Thanh district, Can Tho Province, in a field dry seeded with variety 1960. Rice showed ufra symptoms 40 d after sowing. Two benomyl and water solutions were tested: 0.1 and 0.2% ai sprayed at a rate of 500 liters/ha. An untreated control was the third treatment.

Fields were cultivated following farmers' practices. Experiments were laid out in a randomized complete block design with four replications using 7- × 7-m plots for the first experiment and 10- × 10-m plots for the second experiment. In the first experiment, 10 hills/plot were collected at rice crop maturity for nematode analysis. In the second experiment, five crop cuts of 20- × 20-cm were collected at random from each plot 1 d before, and 10 and 20 d after benomyl treatments. In both experiments, nematodes were extracted from all of the stems collected. Results were analyzed using ANOVA. Means were separated using DMRT.

D. angustus infestation was low in the first experiment, most probably because of late flooding and low water level during the flood. Results indicate,

however, that none of the benomyl treatments controlled the nematode (Table 1). In the second experiment, *D. angustus* numbers were significantly lower in benomyl-treated plots than in

untreated plots at both sampling times (Table 2). Benomyl, however, failed to control the nematode effectively and nematode counts per stem remained high. ■

Table 1. Number of *D. angustus*/hill observed at rice crop maturity after benomyl treatments. Long Thanh My, Thu Duc district, Ho Chi Minh City, Vietnam.

Treatment	<i>D. angustus</i> /hill ^a (no.)
T1 Untreated	7.6 a ^b
T2 Seed treatment by soaking for 24 h in a solution of benomyl at 0.1% ai	8.4 a
T3 T2 + spraying at 30 DT ^c with a solution of benomyl at 0.1 ai at a rate of 400 dm ³ /ha	26.6 a
T4 Seedling treatment by spraying with a solution of benomyl at 0.1 ai 2 d before transplanting at a rate of 240 dm ³ /ha	10.7 a
T5 T4 + spraying at 30 DT with a solution of benomyl at 0.1 ai at a rate of 400 dm ³ /ha	2.6 a
T6 Spraying at 30 DT with a solution of benomyl at 0.1 ai at a rate of 400 dm ³ /ha	17 a
T7 T6 + spraying at flowering with a solution of benomyl at 0.1 ai at a rate of 500 dm ³ /ha	4.2 a
T8 Spraying at 21 d after flooding with a solution of benomyl at 0.1 ai at a rate of 400 dm ³ /ha	29.7 a
T9 Spraying at flowering with a solution of benomyl at 0.1 ai at a rate of 500 dm ³ /ha	11.5 a

^aMean of 4 replications. ^bMeans followed by a common letter are not significantly different at the 5% level by DMRT.

^cDays after transplanting.

Table 2. Number of *D. angustus* observed/stem before and after spraying benomyl at two concentrations 40 d after sowing. Dong Phu, Chau Thanh district, Can Tho Province, Vietnam.

Treatment	<i>D. angustus</i> /stem ^a (no.)		
	1 d before treatment	10 d after treatment	20 d after treatment
Control (no benomyl spray)	33 a	83 a	64 a
Benomyl 0.1% ai	30 a	45 b	44 b
Benomyl 0.2% ai	32 a	42 b	43 b

^aMean of 4 replications. In a column, means followed by a common letter are not significantly different at the 5% level by DMRT.

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Water management

Water management in transplanted wetland rice

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We studied how water management practices affect grain yield and water use efficiency of transplanted rabi (winter) rice. We studied the response of rice crops subjected to various irrigation schedules and determined the most productive schedule when water is a limiting factor.

The experiment was laid out in a completely randomized design during 1989-91. No rain fell during the experiment. Thirty-day-old seedlings of Tellahamsa (120 d) were transplanted into 30-m² plots at Agricultural College Farm, Rajendranagar, Hyderabad. Soil was a clay loam. We applied 100:17.6:24.9 kg NPK/ha in three splits: 1/3 at transplanting, 1/3 at maximum tillering, and 1/3 at panicle initiation. Granulated butachlor (at 1.5 kg ai/ha) mixed with fine sand was applied at 4 d after transplanting (DT) and followed by handweeding at 30-35 DT.

Maintaining 5 cm of water yielded the most rice (5.5 t/ha) in the experiment but required 1,530 mm of the water. Applying 5 cm of water at 2 d after disappearance of ponded water (DADPW) did not reduce yield significantly, but it saved considerable water. 2 DADPW had the highest water use efficiency (5.41 kg grain/ha-mm) among treatments. Other treatments consumed less water than continuous submergence but yielded significantly less (see table). Severe cracks developed in these treatments and water stress occurred during and after panicle initiation. ■